

REALIZATION OF THE CREATIVE POTENTIAL OF YOUTH IN MODERN CONDITIONS

Umarkulova Diyora

3rd year student, Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Uzbekistan, Tashkent city.

sanjarovnad23@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8384457>

This article underscores the pressing importance of nurturing the creative potential of young individuals in contemporary society. It highlights the role of youth as torchbearers of new ideas and champions of innovation. The article discusses the significance of fostering creativity and entrepreneurship in tandem for personal and financial success.

Key words: Creative potential, youth development, creativity, entrepreneurship, teamwork, civic skills, life skills.

РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА МОЛОДЕЖИ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ

Аннотация. В этой статье подчеркивается насущная важность развития творческого потенциала молодых людей в современном обществе. В нем подчеркивается роль молодежи как носителей новых идей и поборников инноваций. В статье обсуждается важность развития креативности и предпринимательства в тандеме для достижения личного и финансового успеха.

Ключевые слова: творческий потенциал, развитие молодежи, креативность, предпринимательство, командная работа, гражданские навыки, жизненные навыки.

At present, the development of the creative potential of young people is one of the most relevant areas of pedagogical research, which is associated with the growing demand of modern society for a socially active, creative, harmoniously developed personality, capable of making creative decisions and being responsible for their implementation. In sociology, the importance of the category "youth" is emphasized due to the fact that it is a conductor of new ideas, initiatives, acts as a bearer of the latest knowledge and creativity.

We consider the concept of "creative potential" of youth as a combination of people's abilities and their activity in setting and solving new creative tasks, showing initiative and entrepreneurship in innovative activities, contributing to the self-development of the individual and his professional growth. For the realization and development of the subject in creative activity and, in particular, for the development of his creative potential, freedom is a necessary condition.

One of the factors influencing the development of creative abilities is the recognition of the value of creativity by young people themselves. Therefore, at present, it seems important to carry out work in this direction, it is necessary to create such conditions that would contribute to the development of young people's qualities and inclinations, which are distinguished as characteristic features of a creative personality. Therefore, to improve the conditions for the development of the creative potential of young people, the government should offer:

- to intensify the work of the education system to identify and support gifted and talented youth, develop and realize their creative abilities;

- to create modern learning conditions in institutions of additional education, allowing students to fully disclose and realize their abilities and skills;
- organize leisure activities that will meet the interests of young people.

Thus, the creative potential of young people should be considered as a resource that is able to develop and be realized under certain conditions, having a significant impact on the development of modern society. The intersection of creativity and entrepreneurship is a powerful force that can lead to both personal fulfillment and financial success.

To begin with, the key to success lies in identifying a shared vision among the members of the creative team. When embarking on a joint project, it is essential to establish a clear and unified goal that resonates with everyone involved. This common purpose will serve as the guiding light throughout the creative process, ensuring that the project remains cohesive and focused. Next, let's emphasize the importance of open communication and a supportive atmosphere within the team. Each member should feel empowered to share their unique ideas and perspectives without fear of judgment. A collaborative environment fosters a melting pot of creativity, where diverse viewpoints converge to produce extraordinary outcomes.

Furthermore, effective delegation of roles and responsibilities plays a crucial role in realizing creative ideas while ensuring productivity. It's essential to identify each person's strengths and assign tasks accordingly, allowing individuals to focus on what they do best. This way, the team can efficiently tackle various aspects of the project, whether it's ideation, execution, marketing, or financial management.

In order to generate revenue, it's crucial to combine creativity with practicality. While artistic expression is at the heart of the project, a strategic approach to marketability and commercial viability must also be adopted. Understanding the target audience, conducting market research, and crafting a solid business plan will help align creativity with economic sustainability.

It's worth noting that in the pursuit of financial success, compromise may arise. However, striking a balance between creative integrity and market demands is vital. It is possible to preserve the essence of original ideas while adapting them to meet the preferences of the intended audience.

As with any entrepreneurial endeavor, persistence, and adaptability are essential traits. The creative process may encounter challenges and obstacles, but a determined and flexible approach will ensure progress and growth.

There are several useful ways to strengthen the civic and life skills of young people, and both the state and local communities can play an important role in this process. Here are some ways:

1. Education: Schools and educational institutions can provide students with opportunities to develop their civic and life skills through curricular and extracurricular activities.
2. Volunteerism: Encouraging young people to volunteer in their communities can help them develop a sense of responsibility and civic duty.
3. Mentorship: Providing young people with positive role models who can help guide them through life can be an effective way to develop their life skills.
4. Youth programs: Communities can provide young people with access to programs that can help them develop skills such as leadership, teamwork, and communication.

5. Community involvement: Encouraging young people to get involved in local community organizations can help them develop a sense of belonging and a desire to make a positive impact in their communities.

6. Support services: Providing young people with access to support services such as counseling, mental health services, and career guidance can help them develop the skills they need to succeed in life.

7. Policy initiatives: The state can implement policies and initiatives that support the development of civic and life skills in young people, such as funding for youth programs and initiatives that promote community involvement and volunteerism.

Overall, a combination of these strategies can be effective in strengthening the civic and life skills of young people, and both the state and local communities have an important role to play in this process.

It is known from the history of any state that the intensive development of the country, its achievements, the well-being of the people depend on the level of attention paid to the education and upbringing of the younger generation. In this context, youth issues in Uzbekistan are among the priorities in the policy of the republic.

It is also deeply symbolic that the first legislative act signed by Shavkat Mirziyoyev as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was the Law of September 14, 2016 “On the State Youth Policy”. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2018 “On the State Program “Yoshlar - kelajagimiz”” has become an important document aimed at improving the efficiency of activities in this area. In particular, in accordance with this decree, the Yoshlar – kelajagimiz Foundation was established under the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, In short, the state youth policy in Uzbekistan, pursuing clear goals and gradually implemented on the basis of comprehensive measures, continues consistently. As part of five important initiatives, 2.9 million students in educational institutions are involved in various clubs (sports, arts and culture, science, robotics, computer technology, etc.). Based on the American T.E.A.M. up program, master classes have been organized for 3,000 students. In addition, a book club was created and in a short period some 270,000 boys and girls became its members. As part of the Book Challenge project, over 600,000 different books were donated to schools.

An additional 36,000 clubs have been set up to provide meaningful leisure activities for young people and some 874,000 boys and girls are involved in them. Within the framework of five major initiatives, 97,000 art supplies, sports equipment and computers were donated to educational institutions, libraries and training centers. Under the Senate, a Youth Parliament has been created - an advisory body that serves to form a personnel reserve for the country's legislative and executive authorities. In addition, the One Million Programmers project is being effectively implemented in our country. In 2021-2022, more than 300,000 young people received free training in the basics of computer programming. This is also the focus of the Youth Parliament.

In summary, fostering the creative potential of young people is crucial for societal progress. Combining creativity and entrepreneurship can lead to personal and financial success. Strengthening civic and life skills involves education, volunteerism, mentorship, youth programs, community involvement, support services, and policy initiatives. Uzbekistan's youth policies demonstrate a commitment to empowering its youth. Investing in youth development ensures a brighter future.

e, S. Team-based learning in online education: the development of students' creative thinking skills in digital art. *Educ Inf Technol* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11808-3>

t

t

p

p

p

p

y

w

w

y

e

a

a

a

p

y

e

h

n

y

e

b

w

b

g

k

d

y

e

b

a

k

i

h

o

leader

entrepreneurs

y

e

m

o

k

i

s